

The order of stability constant at 20° has been observed to be $\text{Sm}^{3+} > \text{Nd}^{3+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} \approx \text{Ce}^{3+} \approx \text{La}^{3+}$. A better separation of $\log K_1$ values amongst Pr^{3+} , Ce^{3+} and La^{3+} has been observed at 30° and 40° where it follows the order $\text{Sm}^{3+} > \text{Nd}^{3+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} > \text{Ce}^{3+} > \text{La}^{3+}$.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been determined by using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation. These are summarised in Table 1. The value of free energies of formation becomes more negative with increase in temperature. This shows that the complex formation process is spontaneous and the spontaneity increases with increase in temperature. The formation of all the complexes is an endothermic process and it explains the increase in the values of constants with rise in temperature. The complex formation is favoured by the increase in the entropy of the system. It is indicated by the positive values ΔS in all the cases. The low values of formation constants, free energy of formation, and enthalpy changes shows that these metals have less tendency to form complexes with glycyl-DL-valine.

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Rh(III) and Ru(III) Complexes of the Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

A. K. NIGAM*

Department of Chemistry, D.B.S. College, Dehradun
and

G. D. TIWARI

Department of Chemistry, V. S. S. D. College, Kanpur

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THE ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of a number of metal ions by the authors¹⁻⁷. The present investigation deals with the Rh(III) and Ru(III) complexes of the ligand. Investigations have indicated that the ligand reacts with these metals at pH ranging from 7.5 to 10.0 giving precipitate of insoluble metal complexes.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand was prepared by the method of Baguley and Elvidge⁸.

The following stock solutions were prepared.

1. 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline about 0.1% sodium salt solution of the ligand in NaOH.
2. $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Johnson-Matthey Co.). A 0.25 W/V solution of hydrated salt in water.
3. $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, as above.

Preparation of Complexes :

A freshly filtered soln. of the ligand was added in excess to soln. No. 1. A yellow brown ppt. of rhodium complex was obtained. It was digested on a water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered, washed with water for several times and then with alcohol, dried at 70 to 105° in an air oven.

In the case of ruthenium(III) a black ppt. was obtained under similar conditions.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicates the metal to ligand ratio as 1:3. Both the complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The infrared spectra of the complexes and the ligand were examined to establish the exact structure of the complexes. The infrared spectra indicates the presence of $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and $\nu(\text{M-S})$ bonds in both the complexes. Coordination of thio-carbonyl sulphur to the metal ion is also clearly indicated; it also indicates the absence of N-H bond in the two complexes. Thus it may easily be concluded that the Rh and Ru ion in the

*Address for correspondence.

complexes are coordinated through both thiocarbonyl sulphur and the nitrogen atom of the ligand. This indicates that Rh and Ru form an inner complex type structure. The reflectance spectra of the complexes was also examined. Both the complexes were found to be insoluble in water and most of the organic solvents. Thus on the basis of analytical, infrared, magnetic moment and reflectance data octahedral configuration have been proposed for the rhodium and ruthenium (III) complexes.

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Thiomalate Complexes of Some Divalent Metal Ions

NIRADA KUMARI MOHANTY

Department of Chemistry, Ispat College, Rourkela

and

R. K. PATNAIK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-8, (Orissa)

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IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on thiomalate complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III), we report in this paper the results of our studies on the interaction of Be(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) with thiomalic acid by pH titration method.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the investigations were of AnalaR grade. The metals were estimated gravimetrically from their respective salt solutions by standard methods. Ionic strength of 0.1M was maintained by the addition of suitable quantity of NaClO₄ to the

solutions. All experiments were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere using a Marconi pH meter. pH titration of 50 ml of solutions containing metal salt and thiomalic acid in different proportions against 0.1 M NaOH were performed at 31°±0.5°.

pH titration of 50 ml of solutions containing 0.005 gm moles of NaClO₄ and

A — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid

B₁ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid and 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of MnSO₄

B₂ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of Co(ClO₄)₂

B₃ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of NiSO₄

B₄ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of ZnSO₄

B₅ — 3.125 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of thiomalic acid + 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ gm. moles of Be(ClO₄)₂

against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide.

Results and Discussion

The amount of acid liberated during complex formation between M²⁺ ions (where M=Be, Mn, Co, Ni and Zn) and thiomalic acid, remains the same even if the metal to ligand ratio is increased from 1 : 1.25 to 1 : 5 which indicates the formation of 1 : 1 type of complex. The reaction taking place due to the interaction of these divalent metal ions with thiomalic acid can be represented as

$$\text{Hence, } K = \frac{[C][H^+]^n}{[M^{2+}][H_3TML]} \quad \dots (2)$$

It can be shown as in the citrate complex of cadmium²